

Prospects & potential of biobutanol production integrated with organophilic pervaporation – A techno-economic assessment

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Engineering guidelines for pervaporation units are provided for ABE production.
- The effects of permeate pressure and cooling were taken into account.
- a pervaporation module purchase price of 50–100 € m⁻² should be targeted.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The technical feasibility of integrating ABE fermentations with organophilic pervaporation has been described and demonstrated numerous times. However, engineering guidelines for integration of pervaporation with fermentation are currently not available. A novel calculation procedure to size pervaporation units in function of carbohydrate concentration in the feed is elaborated in detail. The overall energetic and economic outlook are less investigated and remain unclear. Furthermore, the effect of permeate pressure and cooling are frequently ignored. Therefore, the advantages and economic outlook of such an integration are estimated and calculated for fermentative *n*-butanol production at a capacity of 100 ktonnes per year. Biobutanol production costs for two cases were calculated. The base-case consists of a multi-stage acetone-butanol-ethanol fermentation with default downstream processing. The alternative is a continuous hybrid process where default downstream processing is complemented with organophilic pervaporation for recovery of solvents during the fermentation. Bare pervaporation module costs were estimated to ensure improved economics in comparison to the base-case. Equal installed costs for both cases are reached at a pervaporation module purchase price of 176 € m⁻² for a composite POMS membrane. To derisk this potential large scale organophilic pervaporation application, a module purchase price of 50–100 € m⁻² should be targeted.

1. Introduction

n-Butanol is a bulk chemical amongst others used as an industrial solvent and as an ingredient in paint, coatings and adhesives. Currently, its main production route is the petrochemical oxo synthesis, starting

from propene. For a number of reasons, the older established acetone-butanol-ethanol (ABE) fermentation enjoyed and still enjoys academic, industrial, and military interest in waves throughout the last decades [1,2]. Typically, *C. acetobutylicum*, *C. beijerinckii*, *C. saccharobutylicum* and *C. saccharoperbutylacetonicum* are used in industrial ABE

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Abbreviations

<i>A</i>	pervaporation surface [m ²]	<i>IRR</i>	Internal Rate of Return
<i>ABE</i>	Acetone-Butanol-Ethanol	<i>ISPR</i>	<i>in situ</i> product recovery
<i>B</i>	butanol	<i>J</i>	flux [g m ⁻² h ⁻¹]
<i>BkW</i>	brake power [kW]	<i>J_{ABE}</i>	ABE flux [g m ⁻² h ⁻¹]
<i>C</i>	concentration [g L ⁻¹]	<i>J_B</i>	butanol flux [g m ⁻² h ⁻¹]
<i>C_{B,3}</i>	butanol concentration in the third fermentor [g L ⁻¹]	<i>J_{water}</i>	water flux [g m ⁻² h ⁻¹]
<i>C_{B,permeate}</i>	butanol concentration in the permeate [g L ⁻¹]	<i>J_i</i>	flux for component <i>i</i> [g m ⁻² h ⁻¹]
<i>C_{B,total}</i>	average butanol concentration from effluent from third fermentor and permeate flow [g L ⁻¹]	<i>MEE</i>	Multiple Effect Evaporator
<i>C_{carb,F}</i>	carbohydrate concentration in the feed [g L ⁻¹]	<i>MM</i>	Million (mille mille)
<i>C_{carb,3}</i>	carbohydrate concentration in the third fermentor [g L ⁻¹]	<i>M. W.</i>	molecular weight
<i>C_{i,fermentor}</i>	concentration of compound <i>i</i> in the fermentor [g L ⁻¹]	<i>NPV</i>	Net Present Value
<i>C_p</i>	f.o.b. purchase cost	<i>NRG</i>	energy
<i>CEPCI</i>	chemical engineering plant cost index	<i>NRTL</i>	non-random two-liquid model thermodynamic model
<i>CFM</i>	cubic feet per minute	<i>P</i>	productivity [g L ⁻¹ h ⁻¹]
<i>COP</i>	coefficient of performance	<i>P_{B,ov}</i>	overall butanol productivity [kg m ⁻³ h ⁻¹]
<i>D</i>	dilution rate [h ⁻¹]	<i>PDMS</i>	polydimethylsiloxane
<i>D_{ov}</i>	overall dilution rate [h ⁻¹]	<i>PEBA</i>	polyether block amide
<i>DCFRROR</i>	discounted cash flow rate of return	<i>POMS</i>	poly(octyl methyl siloxane)
<i>E</i>	ethanol	<i>PTMSP</i>	poly[1-(trimethylsilyl)-1-propyne]
<i>EROI</i>	energy return on investment	<i>R</i>	ratio of effluent flow to feed flow
<i>F</i>	feed flow [m ³ h ⁻¹]	<i>ROI</i>	return on investment
<i>f. o. b.</i>	free on board	<i>S_{ov}</i>	overall carbohydrate consumption [g L ⁻¹ h ⁻¹]
<i>FS</i>	flow at suction [m ³ h ⁻¹]	<i>SCDS</i>	Simultaneous Correction Distillation System
<i>G</i>	flow rate of component <i>i</i> [kg h ⁻¹]	<i>S. F.</i>	size factor
<i>HHV</i>	higher heating value [MJ L ⁻¹ or MJ kg ⁻¹]	<i>SE</i>	steam economy
<i>HP</i>	horsepower	<i>SF</i>	split factor; ratio of solvents recovered by pervaporation to total solvents produced
<i>HTA</i>	heat transfer area [m ²]	<i>T</i>	temperature (°C)
<i>IF</i>	installation Factor	<i>V</i>	net reactor volume [m ³]
		<i>Y_{B/Carb}</i>	butanol yield [g _{butanol} g _{carb} ⁻¹]

fermentations [3]. While product ratios can be different from strain to strain, the solvent concentration at the end of a fermentation barely exceeds ~2 wt%, leading to high distillation costs, high waste water volumes coming from the effluent of the beer stripper and low productivities due to product inhibition [4,5]. To illustrate this, Mariano et al. [6] calculated the production of 43–86.7 L stillage per L butanol and the consumption of 29.8–47.5 MJ per kg butanol (excluding stillage treatment) in a conventional plant consisting of mainly fermentation and distillation. The quest for increased solvent productivities, decreased process flows and especially decreased energy consumption explain the interest in *in situ* product recovery (ISPR) technologies [7]. A plethora of research results are available on a multitude of ISPR technologies for fermentative *n*-butanol recovery [8].

To the best of our knowledge, introduction of ISPR technologies for fermentative *n*-butanol production on an industrial scale has not materialized yet [other than the Green Biologics plant in Minnesota, USA (personal communication)] due to the financial risks associated with introducing novel technology on large scale, the required in-depth knowledge of fermentation technology and (bio)chemical engineering to size, design and operate an integrated production plant, and last but not least, the petrochemical production route towards *n*-butanol as a competing process [9].

The term pervaporation was first coined in 1917 by Kober [10]. Independently from evolutions in ABE production, pervaporation evolved from a mere scientific observation to full scale industrial processes. In contrast to the more mature and developed hydrophilic pervaporation membranes, organophilic pervaporation selectively removes organics from dilute aqueous streams. The potential of several organophilic pervaporation membranes coupled to solventogenic fermentations has already been thoroughly investigated [11–19]. The flux of a pervaporation module is a determining factor for the capital investment while the separation factor of the used membrane has implications

towards energy consumption and hence operational costs in the production plant. Initially, dense polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) membranes were used by early pioneers resulting in low (solvent) fluxes. To illustrate this, a total flux of 10.40 g m⁻² h⁻¹ was reported by Groot et al. in 1987 [20] and 25.1–34.8 g m⁻² h⁻¹ by Qureshi et al. in 1999 [21]. In the last decade, thin film composite membranes consisting of a selective top layer on a porous support resulted in significantly higher (solvent) fluxes. PDMS can be considered as a reference material for the top layer, but other silicone based polymers (PTMSP [22] and POMS [23]), polyether block amide (PEBA) polymers [24] and liquid membranes [25] were investigated as well. PDMS based membranes are of particular interest as they do not suffer from fouling during more than 27 days of operation, a prerequisite for long-term operations [13,26]. More recently, POMS based membranes proved their superior performance in terms of (solvent) flux and separation factor in comparison to PDMS based membranes during long-term continuous integrated cultivations lasting more than 25 days [27].

A decreased energy consumption is often claimed as an advantage for introducing ISPR, but rarely calculated for the overall process taking into account all process streams [8]. Rigorously calculating the energy consumption for production of bioproducts, particularly of potential biofuels, is an arduous effort, but a necessity to advance emerging technologies that can impact society. Significant savings in steam consumption of 51.7% from fermentation till purified products (from 69.5 MJ kg⁻¹ to 33.52 MJ kg⁻¹ butanol using ChemCAD simulations, excluding pretreatment) in the distillation and evaporator sections of the plant were calculated for a multistage continuous fermentation integrated with organophilic pervaporation (as described in WO2018/015415 A1) in comparison with a conventional continuous fermentation [11,28].

Often neglected aspects in pervaporation are costs associated with maintaining the vacuum and costs associated with cooling the permeate

technology to the next technological readiness level. At this moment, there is no full-scale installation for biobutanol production integrated with pervaporation. This paper describes boundary conditions and bottlenecks for the renewable production of butanol integrated with pervaporation and hence provides a clear path forward to bring a full-scale installation closer to reality.

2. Methods

2.1. Configuration

Previously, it was experimentally shown (on lab scale) that a continuous operation is superior in comparison to fed-batch operation for production of solvents in terms of solvent productivity, solvent concentration in permeate, manual labour and supervision requirements [27]. Therefore, the process under consideration is a continuous one. Several fermentors-in-series are operated in continuous mode as shown in Fig. 1. The carbohydrate concentration in the feed of the process under consideration is 150 g kg^{-1} [11] and decreases from the first to the last fermentor while solvent concentration increases from the first to the last fermentor. The continuous operation using multiple fermentors-in-series emulates the different phases occurring in a batch fermentation, but leads to reductions in downtime and avoids the long lag phase of microbial cultivations [8,38]. The second fermentor is integrated with organophilic pervaporation and is operated at solvent concentrations low enough not to have complete product inhibition, but high enough to allow solvent concentrations in the permeate in excess of 18% (w/w) [27]. The effluent from the second fermentor is sent to a third fermentor where all the remaining carbohydrates are utilized and where solvent titers close to 2% (w/w) are obtained, i.e. what is expected at the end of a batch fermentation.

The full details on Chemcad simulations related to the distillation towers are described by Van Hecke et al. [11]. The NRTL (non-random two-liquid model) thermodynamic model and SCDS (Simultaneous Correction Distillation System) type of column were chosen. The effluent from the third fermentor is sent to a beer stripper (A) where the top stream contains around 18.7% (w/w) solvents and the solvent-depleted bottom stream is sent to a (5 effect) recirculated falling film stillage evaporator to concentrate it to 20% (w/w) of its original volume. A fraction of the permeate from the organophilic pervaporation units (H) is combined with the top stream of the beer stripper and further separated to obtain butanol at a purity of 99.75% (w/w) at the bottoms of distillation tower D, acetone at a purity of 99.03% (w/w) at the top of distillation tower C and ethanol at a purity of 86.96% (w/w) with the remainder being acetone [2.65% (w/w)] and water [10.4% (w/w)] at the bottoms of distillation tower C. Centrifuges and dryers were not considered in base-case and alternative, but introduction of these unit operations would favor the process alternative due to the reduced process streams leading to reduced capital investments.

The heat of condensation released at the condensers of the steam strippers and distillation towers is used to provide the heat of vaporization in the pervaporation units since the organophilic pervaporation is operated at much lower temperatures, i.e. 32–37 °C. Elaborate details on the process configuration can be found in Van Hecke et al. [11] and in the filed patent application WO2018/015415 A1 [28]. A further decrease in steam consumption is obtained here by splitting the pervaporation permeate [1] in a stream [2] containing butanol and water condensed before the vacuum pump (G) and sent to the decanter (F) and a stream [3] enriched in acetone, butanol and ethanol sent to the second distillation tower [B]. The plant described here is primarily intended for conversion of C6 carbohydrates present in corn mash, wheat, sugar cane, sugar beet, etc. The European Union lifted production quotas for sugar in 2017. The cost levels to produce sugar in North-West Europe are already amongst the lowest in the world due to increasing crop and sugar yields and due to improved production efficiencies. The fields are mainly located in the same region as the

Antwerp-Rotterdam-Rhine-Ruhr-Area chemical cluster and could lead to an interesting complementarity between agriculture and chemistry. It is expected that cost levels will decrease further due to the lifting of quotas [39]. The same reactor configuration can be used as well for second generation feedstocks containing mixtures of C5 and C6 carbohydrates on the condition that C5 consumption rates and utilization are sufficiently high in the last fermentor (which still proves to be problematic). In the latter case, a dedicated pretreatment facility needs to be foreseen, which will increase energy and capital expenditure. This is not discussed in this manuscript, as the focus is to obtain engineering guidelines for pervaporation units and to determine a feasible pervaporation module cost range and as the cost is expected to be identical for base-case and alternative. Furthermore, the solvent capacity of the plant will be lower than 100 kton per annum due to the limited feedstock availability, transport costs and decreased productivity due to the lower consumption rate of xylose [27] in comparison to glucose. To illustrate this statement, the largest lignocellulosic (ethanol) plant to date located in Iowa (USA) is designed for a 340 000 dry tonne per year of corn stover [40]. Hence, 35 530 tonnes of butanol could be expected per year from the same quantity of corn stover assuming a butanol yield of 0.2 [27] and a carbohydrate content of 52.25% [41] in the dry corn stover. The base-case consists of exactly the same configuration, the only difference being the absence of pervaporation (not drawn). Therefore, the carbohydrate concentration in the feed for the base-case is limited to 60 g kg^{-1} , since this is approximately the maximum concentration that can be converted to solvents without applying ISPR technologies.

In order to estimate the capital costs of any facility, unit operations need to be properly sized. Chemical process simulation software programs are instrumental to size distillation towers and other unit operations routinely used in petrochemistry. The required size of the pervaporation units depends on the ratio of solvents recovered by pervaporation to total solvents produced and indirectly on the carbohydrate concentration in the feed. Hence, key design parameters need to be elaborated in detail to allow sizing of the pervaporation units and fermentors.

2.2. Sizing of fermentors

The total required fermentor volume can be sized by calculating the ratio of the butanol production to the overall butanol productivity:

$$\text{Total size fermentors } [\text{m}^3] = \frac{\text{Butanol production } (\text{kg h}^{-1})}{P_{B,ov} (\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1})} \quad (1)$$

The number of production fermentors can then be obtained by dividing the “total size of the fermentors” by the size of the production fermentors (3300 m^3). Fermentors for the inoculation train need to be provided as well. Steady-state conditions are assumed in the following equations.

The overall butanol productivity $P_{B,ov}$ is:

$$P_{B,ov} = D_{ov} * [C_{B,3} * R + C_{B,permeate} * (1-R)] = D_{ov} * C_{B,total} \quad (2)$$

The factor “R” is the ratio of effluent flow to feed flow and is a measure for the concentration effect of applying pervaporation membranes, while the “total butanol concentration” $C_{B,total}$ is the average butanol concentration from the effluent from the third fermentor and the permeate flow:

$$C_{B,total} = C_{B,3} * R + C_{B,permeate} * (1-R) \quad (3)$$

The overall dilution rate is:

$$D_{ov} = \frac{F}{V_1 + V_2 + V_3} = \frac{D_1 * D_2 * D_3}{D_2 * D_3 + D_1 * D_3 + R * D_1 * D_2} \quad (4)$$

The overall carbohydrate consumption S_{ov} is calculated as:

$$S_{ov} = D_{ov} * (C_{carb,F} - R * C_{carb,3}) \quad (5)$$

with $C_{carb,F}$ and $C_{carb,3}$ the carbohydrate concentration in the feed and the last fermentor respectively.

The overall butanol yield can be calculated as the ratio between overall butanol productivity and overall carbohydrate consumption:

$$Y_{B/carb} = \frac{C_{B,total}}{(C_{carb,F} - R * C_{carb,3})} \quad (6)$$

Finally, the overall carbohydrate utilization (%) is calculated as:

$$\text{Carbohydrate utilization} = \left(1 - R * \frac{C_{carb,3}}{C_{carb,F}}\right) * 100 \quad (7)$$

2.3. Sizing pervaporation units

An increased carbohydrate concentration in the feed is attractive due to the reduced process flows, less waste water production and a lower energy expenditure in the evaporators per kg solvent. Studies dealing with sizing aspects are quite rare, but nevertheless required to allow a rational development of such integrated technologies. For gas permeation, membrane area requirements were calculated by Pan and Habgood (1974) for binary systems. However, to the best of our knowledge, no engineering guidelines are currently available to size pervaporation units based on butanol capacity and carbohydrate concentration in the feed. Therefore, the following methodology was developed.

The required pervaporation surface can be defined as:

$$A = \frac{\text{butanol flow in permeate [kg h}^{-1}\text{]}}{\text{butanol flux [kg m}^{-2}\text{ h}^{-1}\text{]}} \\ = SF * \frac{\text{total butanol production [kg h}^{-1}\text{]}}{J_B \text{ [kg m}^{-2}\text{ h}^{-1}\text{]}} \quad (8)$$

The split factor SF is defined as the ratio of butanol recovered by pervaporation to the total butanol produced.

$$SF = \frac{C_{B,permeate} * (1-R)}{C_{B,3} * R + C_{B,permeate} * (1-R)} \quad (9)$$

Through substitution with Eq. (3) in Section 2.2:

$$SF = \frac{C_{B,total} - C_{B,3} * R}{C_{B,total}} \quad (10)$$

If all carbohydrates are consumed:

$$C_{B,total} = Y_{B/carb} * C_{carb,F} \quad (11)$$

Then, through substitution the split factor SF becomes:

$$SF = \frac{Y_{B/carb} * C_{carb,F} - C_{B,3} * R}{Y_{B/carb} * C_{carb,F}} \quad (12)$$

The fluxes for compound i can be estimated by applying the following formula:

$$J_i = \text{slope}_i * C_{i,fermentor} \quad (13)$$

To estimate the slope, linear regression was applied to experimental data originating from a previous study [27] (see Section 3.2). The linear regression models were created using the *fitlm* algorithm in MATLAB (R2016a, MathWorks, Natick, Massachusetts, United States). The 90% confidence interval of the slope is reported as well and is computed such that the true value of the slope (with repeated experimentation) falls within that interval with a probability equal to 0.9.

The factor R in Eq. (12) is the ratio of effluent flow to feed flow. R can also be written as:

$$R = \frac{F - J * A}{F} \quad (14)$$

The total flux is defined as:

$$J = J_{ABE} + J_{water} \quad (15)$$

The feed flow can be calculated as (if all carbohydrates are consumed):

$$F = \frac{\text{butanol production (kg h}^{-1}\text{)}}{Y_{B/carb} * C_{carb,F}} \quad (16)$$

Hence, when calculating the required pervaporation surface using formula (8), (12), (14) and (16) a problem arises since the required pervaporation surface is needed to calculate the ratio of effluent flow to feed flow R . Therefore, an iteration procedure has to be applied. To estimate the required pervaporation surface for a 100,000 tonnes n -butanol facility in function of carbohydrate concentration in the feed:

Assume $R = 1$;

SF is calculated using formula (12);

A is calculated using formula (8);

R is calculated using formula (14) & (16);

Steps 2 to 4 are repeated until a convergence criterion is reached ($|R_{new} - R_{old}| < 1e-6$);

2.4. Cost calculations

Installation factors for individual pieces of equipment were taken from Kazi [42]. An installation factor of 2.6 is assumed for the pervaporation units. Engineering and supervision costs, construction expenses, contractor's fees and working capital are assumed to be 32%, 34%, 23% and 74% of purchased equipment cost, respectively. Purchase costs for storage tanks, steam strippers and multiple effect evaporators were calculated as instructed by Seider et al. [43] and Lambert et al. [44].

Electrical costs were ignored for the base-case but the electrical costs for operating the vacuum pumps and coolers (for condensing the permeate vapours) are taken into account for the alternative. The electricity price is estimated to be $3.0556E-5$ € kJ^{-1} excluding value added tax.

Prices for the fermentors were estimated from quotes from Mueller from 2009 (CEPCI of 521.8) [45]. All purchase prices were corrected to 2016 prices (CEPCI of 541.7). An average exchange rate in 2016 of 1€ to 1.11\$ was used where required. Molasse containing 55% fermentable carbohydrate at 100€ per ton was taken as substrate for the fermentation. A steam price (at 3 bar) of 15€ per ton was assumed. The coproducts in both cases are valorized at 780€ per ton acetone and 500€ per ton ethanol (lower than the market value for ethanol since it is not completely purified yet). It is assumed that the concentrated fermentation broth (from the MEE) can be valorized as fertilizer or animal feed. It is currently not foreseen in the calculations, but when valorized, it can reduce the rational butanol production price further.

3. Results

3.1. Sizing of fermentors

Conservative overall butanol productivities of $0.31 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ for the base-case and $0.42 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ for the process alternative were used based on a series of long-term experimental continuous conversions [27]. Therefore, the total (net) fermentor size is 38156 m^3 (12 production fermentors of 3300 m^3 ; 96% filled) and 28345 m^3 (9 production fermentors of 3300 m^3 ; 96% filled) for both cases. In the base-case, 4 batteries of 3 fermentors each are required to produce 100 kton n -butanol per year, while only 3 batteries of 3 fermentors each are required in the integrated case. An inoculation train is required to inoculate the first production fermentor (not drawn on Fig. 1). To this end, seed fermentors of 33 L, 330 L, 3300 L, 33 m^3 and 330 m^3 are foreseen in the design of the production plant. Only one inoculation train is foreseen in both cases for sequential inoculation of the different batteries.

3.2. Sizing of pervaporation units

3.2.1. Pervaporation surface

The butanol flux depends on the butanol titer in the fermentor [11,13,27]. In continuous conditions, steady-state conditions prevail. Therefore, the required pervaporation surface can be sized by assuming constant butanol titers in the fermentor which in turn lead to a constant butanol flux. The higher the butanol concentration in the fermentor, the lower the productivity due to inhibition, but the higher the solvent composition in the permeate. This trade-off needs to be kept in mind in the design phase and when selecting a proper butanol concentration working point. Butanol (and other solvent) fluxes in function of butanol (and other solvent) titers can be estimated by applying Eq. (13). The slopes with their 90% confidence intervals are reported in Table 1 for two membranes (with PDMS and POMS as top layer) and are based on previously published experimental data [27]. The water flux for the PDMS based membrane is constant in the entire studied solvent range ($\sim 580 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$). The evolution of water flux is less clear for the POMS based membrane, but can be assumed constant from 10 g L^{-1} solvents in the fermentor ($780.3 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$).

By further applying the methodology elaborated above in the method section, a simulation was performed of the surface “A”, the split factor “SF” and the ratio of effluent flow to feed flow “R” (for the 100 kton *n*-butanol production facility) using POMS composite membranes. The results are graphically shown in Fig. 2. The following input (based on previously executed experiments) was used for sizing the pervaporation units: butanol yield $Y_{B/Carb} = 0.20 \text{ g g}^{-1}$ [27]; $C_{B,2} \sim 10 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ and $C_{ABE,2} \sim 14 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$; hence the butanol flux J_B and total flux J are estimated as $164 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $1018 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ respectively based on the empirical correlations developed above; $C_{B,3} = 12 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$.

The ratio of effluent flow to feed flow R decreases in function of the carbohydrate concentration and this (obviously) implicates that the fermentor effluent will be concentrated more at higher initial carbohydrate concentrations due to pervaporation. At higher feedstock concentrations, a higher pervaporation surface is required as well due to the increasing split factor SF . While Fig. 2 provides a stimulus for further abstract thinking, the carbohydrate concentration in the feed is fixed to 150 g kg^{-1} for this cost calculation. The split factor is 0.64 under these conditions. Furthermore, $47\,060 \text{ m}^2$ of pervaporation surface is required for a 100 kton *n*-butanol facility. Since the fermentation section consists of 3 batteries containing 3 fermentors each (see paragraph above), a pervaporation surface of $15\,687 \text{ m}^2$ per battery is required. The pervaporation membranes are coupled to the second of the three fermentors (see Fig. 1). Hence the specific surface area (ratio of pervaporation surface to fermentor volume) is $4.98 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-3}$.

3.2.2. Vacuum pumps

The power consumption of the vacuum pumps due to the presence of the non-condensable gases CO_2 and H_2 should not be ignored. It has important consequences for selection of a feasible permeate pressure working point [27]. Around 3.95 mol of CO_2 and 2.41 mol of H_2 are produced per mole of butanol [46]. It is expected that these are (partially) removed by pervaporation and hence contribute to the power consumption of the vacuum pumps and lead to much larger vacuum pumps in comparison to the situation where no non-condensables are expected. As mentioned in the introduction and in WO2018/015415 A1 [28], the permeate [1] is split in a stream [2] containing mainly butanol and water condensed before the vacuum pump(s) and a stream [3] enriched in acetone, butanol and ethanol passing the vacuum pump and condensed in a second condenser. Therefore, the following components need to be evacuated by the vacuum pumps in a 100 kton biobutanol plant: 2942 kg h^{-1} butanol, 2762 kg h^{-1} acetone, 169 kg h^{-1} ethanol, 4733 kg h^{-1} water. In total $27\,920 \text{ kg h}^{-1}$ CO_2 and 780 kg h^{-1} H_2 are generated in the plant. Since it is hard to estimate how much will be removed through the pervaporation units and how much will be removed by the fermentor gas exhaust lines, different scenarios were

calculated where 100%, 60%, 30% and 15% of non-condensables (CO_2 and H_2) will be removed by the vacuum pumps.

3.2.2.1. Vacuum pump operating costs. The brake power in kilowatts (BkW) for reciprocating vacuum pumps is estimated as [47]:

$$BkW = 3.974 * (S.F.)^{0.963} \quad S.F. = 1.0-25 \quad (17)$$

The size factor is calculated as follows:

$$S.F. = \frac{2.2 * \text{air equivalent flow rate (kg h}^{-1}\text{)}}{\text{operating pressure (mmHg)}} \quad (18)$$

The air equivalent flow rate can be calculated as:

$$\text{Air equivalent flow rate} = \sum_{i=1}^n G_i * \sqrt{\frac{(273.15 + T) * MW_{\text{air}}}{293.15 * MW_i}} \quad (19)$$

where G_i = flow rate of component i [kg/h]; T = temperature of the process gas; MW_i = molecular weight of component i ; MW_{air} = molecular weight of air (28.96 g mol^{-1}).

In case all non-condensables are removed through the pervaporation unit, vacuum costs can be estimated as 0.154 € kg^{-1} butanol at 20 mbar permeate pressure and 0.062 € kg^{-1} butanol at 50 mbar permeate pressure (see Fig. 3). Due to the selected configuration using multiple fermentors in series (see Fig. 1), only a fraction of the generated non-condensables are removed through the pervaporation unit. We assume 60% non-condensable removal to be a more realistic scenario since this approximates the split factor SF (ratio of solvents recovered by pervaporation to total solvents produced). In this case, vacuum costs are estimated as 0.110 € kg^{-1} butanol at 20 mbar permeate pressure (or $\sim 3.6 \text{ MJ kg}^{-1}$ butanol) and 0.044 € kg^{-1} butanol at 50 mbar permeate pressure. The electricity price is estimated to be $3.0556\text{E}-5 \text{ € kJ}^{-1}$ excluding value added tax (see Fig. 4).

Since Eq. (17) is limited to relatively small scale vacuum pumps (in comparison to the required inlet flows) and power equations were not readily available for larger pumps, we have evaluated an alternative calculation method, where it was assumed that the best vacuum pumps can deliver 28 CFM/HP (ratio of cubic feet per minute to consumed horsepower) [48]. Applying this simple rule-of-thumb approximated the results obtained by applying Eqs. (17)–(19) and is therefore not shown.

3.2.2.2. Vacuum pump capital costs. Capital costs were estimated from 10 mbar to 100 mbar permeate pressure. Ryans and Bays (2001) provide typical flow capacities and lower limits of suction pressure [49]. Based on this, a one-stage (oil) sealed pump was selected. These have a typical flow range (at suction conditions) between $5.1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $38\,000 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$. In total, $27\,920 \text{ kg h}^{-1}$ CO_2 and 780 kg h^{-1} H_2 are generated in the plant. Capital costs were calculated for the scenarios where 100%, 60%, 30% and 15% of the generated non-condensables CO_2 and H_2 were evacuated by the vacuum pumps. The mass flows of

Table 1

slopes from Eq. (13) reported with 90% confidence intervals. A permeate pressure of 9–14 mbar and a temperature of 37°C was applied for the PDMS based membranes while a permeate pressure of 20 mbar and a temperature of 32°C was applied for the POMS based membranes. LL: lower limit, UL: upper limit.

Membrane	Compound	Slope ($\text{L m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$)	LL (90%)	UL (90%)
PDMS	Acetone	11.77	10.61	12.93
PDMS	Butanol	10.05	9.04	11.06
PDMS	Ethanol	4.37	3.44	5.30
PDMS	ABE	9.65	8.84	10.46
POMS	Acetone	22.20	20.36	24.04
POMS	Butanol	16.40	15.20	17.60
POMS	Ethanol	6.61	6.10	7.13
POMS	ABE	16.95	15.77	18.14

Fig. 2. Left axis: Membrane surface \blacklozenge ; right axis: split factor SF \blacksquare and ratio of effluent flow to feed flow R \blacktriangle in function of carbohydrate concentration.

Fig. 3. Power consumption of vacuum pumps expressed as MJ electricity per kg butanol produced in the whole plant (left axis), operating costs of vacuum pumps expressed per kg butanol produced in the whole plant (right axis) estimated for reciprocating vacuum pumps. Evacuation of 0% non-condensables (\times); evacuation of 15% non-condensables (\circ); evacuation of 30% non-condensables (\diamond); evacuation of 60% non-condensables (\triangle); evacuation of 100% non-condensables (\square).

Fig. 4. Capital costs of a one-stage sealed liquid-ring pump (in cast iron) in function of permeate pressure and in function of removal percentage of total generated non-condensable gases during fermentation through vacuum pumps. Evacuation of 0% non-condensables (\times); evacuation of 15% non-condensables (\circ); evacuation of 30% non-condensables (\diamond); evacuation of 60% non-condensables (\triangle); evacuation of 100% non-condensables (\square).

all components evacuated by the vacuum pumps were: 3208 kg h⁻¹ butanol, 3011 kg h⁻¹ acetone, 185 kg h⁻¹ ethanol, 5160 kg h⁻¹ water.

The purchase cost C_p of a one-stage liquid seal pump (cast iron) can be estimated in 2016€ as [50]:

$$C_p = 17.31 * (FS)^{0.8383} * \frac{CEPCI_{2016}}{CEPCI_{2014}} = 16.276 * (FS)^{0.8383} \quad (20)$$

FS is the flow at suction in m³ h⁻¹. In the scenario where 60% of the non-condensables are removed through the pervaporation units, a purchase cost of 3.37 MM€ is obtained at 20 mbar permeate pressure while a purchase cost of 1.35 MM€ is obtained at 50 mbar permeate pressure. Since most experimental data is available for 20 mbar permeate pressure and assuming the 60% non-condensable removal ratio to be the real case, 3.37 MM€ purchase costs is used in further calculations.

3.2.3. Cooling costs

The heat released during condensation was estimated to be 32.86 MW [11]. The pervaporation is operated at the same temperature of the fermentation, i.e. 32–37 °C. Therefore, the majority of the heat in the permeate condensers might be removed by cooling water from cooling towers (requiring some energy input to power the circulation pumps and to run fans in the cooling towers). Chilled water (-2 °C) produced by refrigeration units [51] can be used to condense the remainder of the permeate still present as vapour. The cooling profile is presented in Fig. 5.

The composition of the different streams is shown in Table 2.

The required cooling capacity throughout the cooling step is shown in Table 3.

The capacity of the second precondenser (Pre Cond 2) is based on the outlet temperature of the vacuum pump calculated by Chemcad. This is theoretical, without any heat losses. The cooling capacity in reality could be lower. At lab scale, the temperature after the vacuum pump is ambient.

The required capacity and cost of the cooling water can be neglected in comparison with the cost of the chilling water. Hence, the cost of the cooling water is not taken into account.

The cost estimate C_p of a refrigeration plant in (2016) MM€ can be estimated as [52]:

$$C_p = 0.15496 * (P)^{0.695} \quad (21)$$

where P is the required cooling power in GJ h⁻¹. The equation is valid from 0.211 GJ h⁻¹ up to 422 GJ h⁻¹. Hence, the cost for the refrigeration plant is 2.71 MM€.

The electricity consumption can be estimated by assuming a COP of 3.47 [53]. Consequently, the electricity consumption can be estimated as: $\frac{61481 \text{ MJ h}^{-1}}{11900 \text{ kg butanol h}^{-1} * 3.47} = 1.46 \text{ MJ electricity kg}^{-1}$ which corresponds to 0.0446 € kg⁻¹ butanol.

3.3. Falling film stillage evaporator

The f.o.b. purchase cost C_p of a falling film evaporator can be estimated in 2016€ as [54]:

$$C_p = 49415 * (HTA)^{0.55} \quad (22)$$

where HTA is defined as the heat transfer area (in m²). As a general rule-of-thumb, the steam economy is slightly lower than the number of effects. Therefore, the steam economy for the 5 effect evaporator was estimated to be 4.5 while the overall heat transfer coefficient was assumed to be 3.12 kW m⁻² K⁻¹ [55]. The steam economy defines the overall steam consumption as the incoming flows are known. The multiple effect evaporator was sized according to instructions given by Lambert et al. [44]. To this end, mass and heat balances were solved to estimate the required HTA for every effect using the heat transfer equation for conduction.

Fig. 5. Condensation cooling profile. I: stream number; T: temperature (°C); P: pressure (bar); W: Total mass flow (kg/h) (Chemcad, Process Flow Diagram).

Table 2

Composition of the process streams in the cooling step of the process (stream numbers correspond to the ones mentioned in Fig. 5).

Stream No.	1	4	5	9	10
Flow rates in kg/h	Permeate	Liquid Cond	Vent Cond1	Final Liquid	Final vent
Acetone	2795	31	2764	1870	894
Ethanol	190	24	166	158	7
Water	29 920	21 775	8145	8024	121
Carbon dioxide	25 011	14	24 997	910	24 087
<i>n</i> -Butanol	6988	1130	5858	5772	86
Hydrogen	697	0	697	0	697

3.4. Cost calculations for base-case

Table 4 lists the purchase and installed costs in 2016€ for the base-case process and the integrated process. The plant is divided in several sections being storage, fermentation, product recovery and stillage handling for the base-case. The purchase costs are 35.8 MME and installed costs 76.7 MME. The total capital investment is estimated to be 147 MME (including engineering and supervision, construction expenses, contractor's fee, contingency and working capital).

Table 5 lists the manufacturing costs for the base-case and integrated process. These are divided in variable costs (raw material costs, cost of utilities and income generated for byproducts), fixed costs (operating labor, supervision, maintenance, operating supplies, laboratory charges, taxes & insurance, plant overhead) and capital charges calculated per kg butanol. Hence, the rational production price for the base-case is 1580 € per ton biologically derived *n*-butanol (see Table 6).

Subsequently, a (discounted) cash flow analysis was performed [54]. A depreciation period of 10 years was used (straight-line) and the tax rate was fixed to 35%. The cost of capital was assumed to be 15%. At the calculated rational *n*-butanol price of 1580 € per ton, the ROI (10 years) is 26.8% with a NPV (10 years) of 24.9 MME and a DCFROR of 19.5% (10 years).

3.5. Cost calculations for the integrated process

The purchase price of organophilic pervaporation membrane modules was calculated at which the installed costs of the integrated plant (with ISPR) are identical to the installed costs of the continuous plant

Table 3

Cooling capacities. Equipment numbers correspond to the ones mentioned in Fig. 5.

Equip. No.	1	2	5	6	
Utility Name	Cooling water Pre Cond 1	Chilling water Cond 1	Cooling Water Pre Cond 2	Chilling water Cond 2	Total chilling
Outlet temp. (°C)	25	0.001	25	3	
Heat Duty (MJ/h)	−1015.53	−57609.5	−28826.3	−3871.88	−61 481

without ISPR. This was determined to be 176 € m^{−2}. Due to the decreased utility costs (lower steam consumption), the rational price (variable + fixed costs + capital charges) is 7.6% lower at identical capital costs for both process configurations (see Table 5). At a pervaporation purchase price of 369 € m^{−2} an identical rational production price of 1.58 € kg^{−1} is obtained for both cases. An installation factor of 2.6 is assumed. Therefore, an (installed) pervaporation plant including all necessities which costs 458 € m^{−2} pervaporation surface will lead to equal capital costs between base-case and process alternative while an (installed) pervaporation plant of 960 € m^{−2} will lead to an equal butanol production price. More expensive membranes (at similar total and solvent fluxes) are therefore not cost-effective for this application. Table 4 lists the purchase and installed costs in 2016 € for the different sections of the *n*-butanol facility, i.e. storage, fermentation, *in situ* product recovery, product recovery and stillage handling. The fermentation, distillation and stillage handling sections are less capital intensive in the alternative due to the improved solvent productivity and the increased feedstock concentration. However, for a (purchase) pervaporation membrane module cost of 176 € m^{−2}, the capital gains in fermentation, distillation and stillage handling sections are completely offset by the investment in pervaporation units.

A cash flow analysis was performed as well for the integrated process. A depreciation period of 10 years was used (straight-line) and the tax rate was fixed to 35%. The cost of capital was assumed to be 15%. At the calculated rational *n*-butanol price of 1460€ per ton, the ROI is 28.7% with a NPV of 35.8 MME and a DCFROR of 21.8% (for a project lifetime of 10 years), which is higher than in the base-case. Qureshi et al. [56] calculated a butanol production price of 1.04 (2013)\$ for the conversion of wheat straw to butanol for a 150 kton butanol (green-field) facility, taking into account the pretreatment as well. The economies of scale will be offset by increased freight costs of the raw material as also suggested by the currently largest lignocellulosic (ethanol) plant designed for 340 kton per year of feedstock [40]. Therefore, the same authors also calculated the butanol production price for smaller (green-field) plant capacities and reported a price of 2.23 (2013)\$ for a plant capacity of 150 kton wheat straw.

4. Discussion

As mentioned in the introduction already, a plethora of ISPR technologies for butanol recovery is already described in literature leading to different designs. Errico et al. [57] evaluated a hybrid design

Table 4
Purchase and installed costs in 2016€ for base-case and integrated case.

Item	IF	Base-case		Integrated case	
		Purchased Cost (€)	Installed cost in 2016€	Purchased Cost (€)	Installed cost in 2016€
<i>Storage (2 weeks)</i>					
Molasses	2.60	€ 1.030.762	€ 2.679.981	€ 1.030.762	€ 2.679.981
Butanol	2.60	€ 341.901	€ 888.942	€ 341.901	€ 888.942
Acetone	2.60	€ 270.760	€ 703.977	€ 270.760	€ 703.977
Subtotal		€ 1.643.423	€ 4.272.900	€ 1.643.423	€ 4.272.900
<i>Fermentation</i>					
4th seed vessel agitator	1.6	€ 11.132	€ 17.811	€ 11.132	€ 17.811
5th seed vessel agitator	1.6	€ 13.115	€ 20.985	€ 13.115	€ 20.985
Fermentor agitator	1.6	€ 294.391	€ 471.026	€ 220.793	€ 353.269
1st seed fermentor	2.0	€ 16.648	€ 33.296	€ 16.197	€ 32.393
2nd seed fermentor	2.0	€ 35.210	€ 70.420	€ 34.255	€ 68.510
3th seed fermentor	2.0	€ 74.467	€ 148.934	€ 72.448	€ 144.895
4th seed fermentor	2.0	€ 157.494	€ 314.988	€ 153.223	€ 306.446
5th seed fermentor	2.0	€ 666.184	€ 1.332.367	€ 324.059	€ 648.117
Fermentor	2.0	€ 8.453.668	€ 16.907.337	€ 6.168.308	€ 12.336.617
Feed mix tank	2.6	€ 136.821	€ 355.734	€ 136.821	€ 355.734
Broth surge tank	2.6	€ 171.236	€ 445.215	€ 147.869	€ 384.459
Subtotal		€ 10.030.367	€ 20.118.112	€ 7.298.220	€ 14.669.237
<i>In situ product recovery</i>					
Pervaporation	2.6	–	–	€ 8.280.571	€ 21.529.484
Vacuum pumps	1.6	–	–	€ 3.370.000	€ 5.392.000
Refrigeration	1.6	–	–	€ 2.710.000	€ 4.336.000
Subtotal		€ –	€ –	€ 14.360.571	€ 31.257.484
<i>Product recovery</i>					
Steam stripper	3.0	€ 1.218.979	€ 3.656.937	€ 588.323	€ 1.764.968
Acetone-ethanol/butanol split column	3.0	€ 274.627	€ 823.881	€ 304.984	€ 914.951
Ethanol column	3.0	€ 169.645	€ 508.936	€ 169.645	€ 508.936
Water stripper	3.0	€ 157.292	€ 471.877	€ 157.293	€ 471.879
Butanol stripper	3.0	€ 106.973	€ 320.918	€ 106.973	€ 320.918
Subtotal		€ 1.927.516	€ 5.782.549	€ 1.327.217	€ 3.981.652
<i>Stillage handling</i>					
Five effect evaporator	2.1	€ 22.168.612	€ 46.554.086	€ 9.682.499	€ 22.546.376
Total		€ 35.769.918	€ 76.727.648	€ 34.311.930	€ 76.727.648

consisting of extraction with hexyl acetate combined with distillation. In this study, chemical process simulations were conducted without experimental confirmation. Since the selected solvent is slightly soluble in water ($\sim 0.4 \text{ g L}^{-1}$), the toxicity of this solvent towards the producing strain has to be experimentally evaluated to increase the reliability of the simulations. Secondly, solvent losses in the raffinate complicate waste water treatment and are not taken into account in this study. Furthermore, introduction of an organic liquid phase in combination with bioprocesses might lead to the formation of (stable) emulsions, hindering effective downstream processing [58]. Unfortunately, these phenomena cannot be predicted using chemical process simulators. Patraşcu et al. [59] evaluate the downstream processing of the condensate after applying gas stripping to a fermentation process. Consequently, the energy required for gas stripping is unreported. Gas stripping is a robust technology and simple to apply on lab scale. However, electricity consumption for the compressor is rather high for a full scale industrial fermentor (typically 2–3 vvm are applied). The condensation duty is high as well due to the presence of non-condensable gases [60]. These two aspects are frequently ignored, but should not be ignored when evaluating the overall potential of a process. Furthermore, the simulations were based on a concentration of 24% solvents in the condensate. These concentrations are very high for (a one stage) gas stripping and are not mentioned in the referred experimental study either [61]. Finally, under the assumption that it is

possible to reach these high concentrations in the condensate, by logical deduction, it implicates high solvent titers in the fermentor at all times. Hence, a significant fraction of the solvents is left untreated in this configuration leading to increased feedstock costs and an uneconomical process.

Adsorption is another interesting ISPR technology. The crucial issues here are the concomitant adsorption of acetate and butyrate with the solvents of interest. These volatile fatty acids are intermediates in the production of acetone, butanol and ethanol. Many studies can be found where adsorption is evaluated using artificial media, but only few studies address adsorption when coupled to a running fermentation. Nielson and Prather [62] tested a Dowex Optipore SD-2 adsorbent in small batch fermentations. This adsorbent had a high affinity for butanol, but also for organic acids, mainly butyrate. Liu et al. [63] tested a KA-I resin as adsorbent which had a high affinity for butanol and butyrate. The butyrate co-adsorption was reduced by keeping butanol above 6.5 g L^{-1} (but not eliminated). Finally, Wiehn et al. [64] studied macroporous and hydrophobic poly(styrene-codivinybenzene) resin Dowex Optipore L-493 in combination with fermentation. This seems to be a promising candidate as interaction with other products (acetate, butyrate, salts) is negligible. However, as in previous integrated studies, the time scale of the experiment is rather limited (72 h). Biofouling could reduce the surface area for adsorption which will decrease adsorbent capacity. This remains to be investigated in longer-term trials.

Table 5
Manufacturing costs for the base-case and integrated case for a membrane module purchase price of 176 € m⁻².

Item	Basis		Base-case €/kg butanol	Integrated process €/kg butanol
Raw materials				
Nutrients		€/kg butanol	0.02	0.02
Water	0.26	€/1000 L	0.02	0.02
Molasses	100.00	€/ton, 55% sugar	0.91	0.91
		Raw Materials	0.948	0.943
Utilities				
Electricity	0.11	€/kWh	–	0.155
3,5 bar steam (DSP)	15	€/1000 kg	0.35	0.20
3,5 bar steam (multiple effect evaporator)	15	€/1000 kg	0.19	0.08
		Utilities	0.536	0.428
Co-products				
Ethanol	0.50	€/kg ethanol	–0.08	–0.08
Acetone	0.78	€/kg acetone	–0.39	–0.39
		Co-products	–0.473	–0.473
		Total Variable cost	1.011	0.897
Operating labor	30.00	€/man hr, 42 operators	0.106	0.106
Supervision	15.00	% operating labor	0.016	0.016
Maintenance	4.00	% fixed capital cost	0.047	0.046
Operating supplies	15.00	% maintenance	0.007	0.007
Laboratory charges	15.00	% operating labor	0.002	0.002
Taxes & insurance	1.50	% fixed capital cost	0.017	0.017
Plant overhead	60000.00	€/jaar, 22 people	0.028	0.028
		Total fixed cost	0.223	0.222
Capital charges (30% of total capital cost)			0.34	0.34
Rational price (variable + fixed cost + capital charges)			1.58	1.46

Table 6
Comparison of EROIs for bio-ethanol, biobutanol and petrochemical butanol production.

	Ethanol	Biobutanol ^a	Petrochemical butanol ^b
<i>EROI_{cradle-to-nozzle}</i>	0.8–1.6 [71]	–	–
<i>EROI_{plant}</i>	1.39–1.73 [72–77]	0.4–0.7 traditional process [4]; 0.52 in base-case (simulations) [11]; 0.74 in integrated case [28]	–
<i>EROI_{cradle-to-plant gate}</i>	1.11–1.26 [73–75]	–	0.52 [81]

^a All energy allocated to butanol production with coproduction of acetone and ethanol (excluding feedstock preparation).

^b From propylene via *n*-butyraldehyde, Rhodium catalyst (oxo synthesis).

To avoid biofouling, a filtration or centrifugation step can be implemented prior to the adsorption step.

On the other hand, pervaporation tests integrated with fermentation were already conducted for 20–25 days continuously without the need for cell separation (in lab scale experiments), showing the higher technological readiness level in comparison to adsorption.

The design proposed in this manuscript is distinctly different from previously studied techno-economic calculations dealing with fermentations integrated with pervaporation. Kazi et al. [42] studied organophilic pervaporation for ethanol production as a replacement of the beer stripper (hence as a downstream process technology, not as ISPR technology). O'Brien et al. [65] performed a cost calculation for continuous ethanol production integrated with organophilic pervaporation. However, these authors did not take into account the ethanol losses in the bleed which would lead to an increase in feedstock costs per kg of ethanol. The current evaluation takes all process streams into account.

In this calculation exercise, experimental fluxes were used from ~5 L fermentations integrated with lab-scale pervaporation modules (1 or 2

in series) with an exchange surface of 0.009 m² each operated at a cross-flow velocity of 2.19 m s⁻¹. It is clear that large deviations can be expected when extrapolating these experimental data to a (net) fermentor volume of 28 345 m³ and a pervaporation membrane surface of 47 060 m² required for a 100 kton *n*-butanol facility. Therefore, to further advance this technology, these lab-scale experimental fluxes need to be confirmed on pilot scale as a logical next step.

Furthermore, to illustrate the gap between the required membrane surface and the current industrial reality, the largest (hydrophilic) pervaporation plant (to the best of our knowledge) had an installed surface area of 2100 m² and was commissioned in 1988 (Béthéniville, France) for dehydrating ethanol at a daily production of 150 m³ [66]. The composite membranes were in the form of flat sheets in several plate and frame modules [67]. Therefore, development of membranes with higher (solvent) fluxes will decrease the required pervaporation surface further while parallel developments in module design will open these new opportunities. Periodic membrane replacement was not considered. Even though the mild conditions (30–37 °C) are expected to favor a long pervaporation life-time, an assumed lifetime of ten years nevertheless involves a risk for potential investors. Therefore, to derisk this potential large-scale application for organophilic pervaporation, it is advisable to aim for a pervaporation module purchase price in the order of 50–100 € m⁻². It is expected that this price range can be reached as long as the current niche market is able to transform itself into a larger market.

The solvent concentration in the permeate is directly related to the solvent composition in the fermentor. Therefore, on top of applying the design rules elaborated above for sizing the pervaporation units, online control of the solvent concentration in the fermentors is deemed crucial for a more robust operation of the pervaporation unit. Even though high solvent concentrations were already obtained during prolonged periods of time [11,13], large variations in permeate are observed during the initial (fed)-batch periods and during the onset of the continuous regimes [27] (the current practice in most research articles dealing with such integrated designs can be compared to sizing a heating device and subsequently operating it without a thermostat. Even though the

heating device can be well sized, wide temperature fluctuations will still be observed due to external factors). Therefore, a more robust operation is expected when the pervaporation unit would operate between a low set value (to avoid too low solvent concentrations in the permeate demanding too much energy in DSP) and a high set value (as a compromise between solvent inhibition and solvent concentration in the permeate). Online measurements of alcohols in the headspace of the fermentor using e.g. mass spectroscopy would be suitable for this. To the best of our knowledge, this has not been applied before.

A 51.7% decrease in steam consumption (from 69.5 MJ kg⁻¹ to 33.52 MJ kg⁻¹ butanol) was used in this techno-economic assessment based on previous calculations where 18.4% of solvents were assumed in the permeate [11]. This concentration is lower than the results obtained using POMS membranes where ~23 wt% solvents were obtained during 300 h continuous fermentations [27]. Therefore, we think the decreases in steam consumption are estimated conservatively. Furthermore, the current end-of-pipe treatment consists of an energy intensive beer stripper. Replacement of the beer stripper with a more energy-efficient technology able to recover low concentrations of solvents could potentially decrease energy costs further. To this end, implementation of an adsorption column as an end-of-pipe treatment could be advantageous as co-adsorption of butyrate and acetate is not considered as a significant disadvantage. This is inspired by the work of Nijhuis [68] where the removal of trace organics from water by pervaporation is studied. After an economic evaluation, it was concluded that pervaporation alone is not suitable to treat very low effluent concentrations due to the requirement of excessive membrane areas. A hybrid set-up was then discussed where pervaporation was used to remove the bulk of the contaminant and adsorption as an end-of-pipe technology to decrease the organics in the effluent to very low concentrations.

Bio *n*-butanol attracts interest as a renewable chemical. It is also considered as a potential biofuel [1,69]. One of the reasons behind this interest is the higher heat of combustion in comparison to ethanol. To evaluate the potential of a biofuel, the energy return on investment (EROI) as described by Murphy and Hall [70] is an interesting parameter. EROI is defined as:

$$EROI = \frac{\sum \text{of the } E \text{ content of fuels delivered}}{\sum \text{of all the } E \text{ costs of getting those fuels}} \quad (23)$$

Reported EROIs for ethanol range from 0.8 to 1.6 for the corn based process [71]. The energy costs include the energy required in agriculture, feedstock transport, in the ethanol plant and ethanol distribution. To allow a fairer comparison with the butanol case, the ratio of the energy content in ethanol (HHV of 23.6 MJ L⁻¹) to the gross energy consumed solely in the ethanol plant was calculated. This parameter ($EROI_{plant}$) ranges from 1.39 to 1.73 depending on the source [72–77]. It can definitely be considered to allocate credit to the production of acetone and ethanol, but when allocating the entire steam consumption to butanol production (HHV of 36.09 MJ kg⁻¹) using experimental data provided by Ni and Sun [4] (excluding energy needed to harvest and transport the substrate to the plant and the energy required to distribute the butanol, i.e. from plant entrance to gate), the $EROI_{plant}$ of the traditional process is estimated to be in the range of ~0.4–0.7 (excluding electricity consumption in the plant). When recalculating the $EROI_{plant}$ for the traditional process from chemcad simulations (excluding electricity consumption) [11], it is estimated to be 0.52. For the integrated design it is expected that electricity consumption for mainly vacuum pumps and condensers cannot be neglected. Therefore, the following formula was used for the calculation of the $EROI_{plant}$ for the integrated case:

$$EROI_{plant} = \frac{HHV \text{ butanol (MJ kg}^{-1}\text{)}}{NRG_{Steam} + 2.52 * NRG_{Electricity}} \quad (24)$$

NRG_{Steam} is the energy required for the production of steam (per kg

butanol) and $NRG_{Electricity}$ is the consumed electricity (per kg butanol) where the multiplier (2.52) reflects the efficiency of electricity generation [74]. The electricity consumption is assumed to be 1.46 MJ kg⁻¹ butanol for chilling and 3.6 MJ kg⁻¹ butanol for operating the vacuum pumps. The energy required for the production of steam is assumed to be 33.52 MJ kg⁻¹ [28]. Hence, an $EROI_{plant}$ of ~0.74 is obtained, which is 42% higher than the $EROI_{plant}$ from the base-case chemcad calculations. It is significantly lower when compared to the $EROI_{plant}$ for ethanol, which is mainly due to the lower butanol titers and to the coproduction of large amounts of acetone and ethanol. On the other hand, the use of *n*-butanol as an oxygenate has less drawbacks compared to the use of ethanol in diesel, based on tests in a euro 6 engine [78]. It reduced particle emissions up to 43% in blends consisting of 16% *n*-butanol in diesel (by volume) with respect to particle emissions in diesel fuel. Furthermore, *n*-butanol has a higher cetane number [79], a higher viscosity [80] and a higher heating value compared to ethanol. Interestingly, the $EROI_{plant}$ of biobutanol for the integrated case is larger than the $EROI_{cradle-to-plant \text{ gate}}$ for butanol derived from the petrochemical oxo-synthesis [81]. Naturally, the $EROI_{cradle-to-plant \text{ gate}}$ of biobutanol will be lower than the $EROI_{plant}$ of biobutanol, but the current numbers suggest that biobutanol (derived from the integrated case) can stand the comparison with butanol from the oxo-synthesis well from an EROI point of view. Furthermore, the challenges of climate change and energy security can be tackled as well by using renewable oxygenates, even though its exact effects should be quantified properly. Potential strategies to increase $EROI_{plant}$ further are: 1. Increase solvent tolerance to allow increased butanol titers in the fermentor; 2. Strain selection/engineering to decrease ethanol and acetone production; development of membranes with higher separation factors to decrease chilling and distillation costs.

5. Conclusions & perspectives

Engineering guidelines were developed in this manuscript to aid in scaling organophilic pervaporation integrated with fermentation. The economic assessment indicates that a pervaporation module purchase price of 176 € m⁻² leads to equal installed costs for both cases. Nevertheless, an *n*-butanol facility of 100 kton per annum requires a total pervaporation surface of 47 060 m² at a carbohydrate concentration of 150 g kg⁻¹ in the feed. To cope with possible membrane replacement and to derisk this potential large scale organophilic pervaporation application, a module purchase price of 50–100 € m⁻² should be targeted. The following recommendations (in random order) are made to bridge the gap between development and application and to bring this integrated technology to the next level: 1. integrating the required pervaporation surface in a plant whilst also limiting concentration and temperature gradients requires further elaboration; 2. online monitoring for improved process control; 3. polymer research and performance testing of (novel) membranes under relevant conditions; 4. improved module design for this specific application.

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